

How do synaptic dynamics encrypt functional memory?

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Modern *in vivo* studies show that neural circuits evolve primarily through synapse formation and destruction; and that this evolution is a function of experience. Thus, experience-driven memory function is supported by synaptic dynamics. But how? I address this question through a systematic investigation into the literature of synapse dynamics and cortical information storage. I concentrate on the results of modern, high-resolution imaging experiments to extract basic insights into the spatial and temporal systems at work. I review: (1) the geometric foundations to synapse connectivity; (2) *in vivo* data of natural structural synaptic dynamics; and (3) stimulated synapse plasticity. I conclude with a discussion that proposes an original model for explaining how neural circuits encrypt and use sensory information: an electrochemical system of non-linear instructional synapse matrices.

Introduction

The human brain computes electrical information using a dynamic circuit of 10^{11} neurons connected by 10^{15} electrochemical synapse junctions (1). When a neuron is excited, it emits an electrical pulse from the ion channels in its membrane. This electricity diffuses throughout the neuron's axon to activate thousands of synaptic connections with the dendrites of other neurons. In most cases, the synaptic connection is a dendritic spine that is close enough to an axonal bouton to transfer electrically-dictated chemicals across an open

space (2). Each neuron integrates tens of thousands of these post-synapse chemical inputs. The awesome result is a non-linear system with emergent collective computational abilities (3).

But where in this ephemeral electrical storm of sensory processing can we identify the capacity for information to be stored? The answer, at least partially, is that *functional* memory is stored through changes in synapse connections (4). There are two types of changes in synapses that have been identified as memory-harnessing: weight-based and wiring (1). Weight-based changes describe the strengthening or weakening of existing connections, while wiring changes describe the creation or destruction of connections. This distinction is artificial, since such changes are not mutually exclusive, but the clarification is important because this investigation will be limited to considering only the effects of wiring changes. Wiring changes dramatically affect the connectivity matrix of neurons, serving as a potent substrate for encoding memory. But how quickly do these synaptic wiring changes occur, and what are the requisite spatial conditions? In addition, what is the functional relationship between wiring changes and sensory experience? To answer these questions, and thus provide insight into the encryption of memory, I first look at the spatial distances regulating axon-to-dendrite relationships that are critical to synapse formation in §2. In §3 I review *in vivo* studies of naturally occurring synapse dynamics, before addressing the data from stimulated synaptic plasticity in §4. Finally, in §5, I attempt to identify and analyze the physical units of a neural substrate for learning to suggest a biophysical relationship between synapse formation and functional memory.

Geometric Limits to New Connections

Understanding connectivity in the brain begins by building a spatial framework. Using recent technological advances, a quantitative geometrical map of the brain is attainable with unprecedented precision. Specific cells can be targeted electrophysiologically or genetically to express

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unusual fluorescence using biocytin or green fluorescent protein (GFP). These labeled cells can then be imaged at high resolution using traditional, confocal or two-photon microscopes (5). Figure 1 shows an exquisite *in vivo* example of this imaging capability: a real image of a living mouse neuron with spiny dendrites protruding.

Figure 1 Spatially examining a mouse neuron *in vivo*. The neuron has been genetically encoded to be fluorescent, allowing the visibility of several spiny dendrites extending from its membrane. This *in vivo* image using two-photon microscopy was originally published in (6).

Upon imaging, we can follow up with computer-based systems to yield three-dimensional reconstructions of cell shapes. The storage capacity of a neural network depends in part on the proximity of axons with dendrites, because this will determine whether a synapse connection can be made. If an axon is within a critical distance s of a dendrite, which is defined to be the maximum length of a synapse, then it is possible for an electrochemical connection to be made (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Potential synapse connections between an axon and a dendrite. **a**, Three-dimensional reconstruction of a dendrite (red) and an axon (blue). **b**, Magnification of the arbor overlap in the region. Potential synapses between the two arbors are shown with small black circles. **c**, Further magnification of a potential synapse in **b**. A potential synapse is where an axonal branch is present within distance, s , of a dendrite. Scale bar: 100 μm in **a**, 30 μm in **b**, and 3 μm in **c**. This figure was originally published in (5).

Just how often do we find potential synapses becoming real synapses? In answering this question it is important to distinguish between two different types of synaptic partners. First, we focus on synapses that require only minimal physical growth, such that an axon and a dendrite is already within a distance s ($\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ or less) of each other. This case only requires the growth of a dendritic *spine* or axonal *bouton* to bridge the gap. Data show the average ratio of actual to potential synapses for various cortical structures to be 0.1–0.3 (7).

But this ratio says nothing about the density of these connections. How common are potential synapse connections that require only minimal

growth? To extrapolate this value into a physical context, we can determine the number of potential synapse connections for a single pair of neurons by looking at reconstructions of axonal and dendritic arbors (8). This approach yields that any two neurons within a few hundred micrometers of each other typically have at least one potential synapse connection between them. This means that the only requirement for these neurons to become electrochemically connected is the simple extension of a small spine or bouton. So it follows that the cortex is very physically potent in restructuring its connections, quickly and easily.

The second case for synapse connection is more expensive, requiring growth of full axon or dendritic branches, instead of subtle spine or bouton protrusions from each of the two. A valid question is whether the adult brain even retains the capacity for dendritic and axonal growth in the first place. Past studies using the common Golgi technique would indicate there is a flux of branch growth (9). But the problem with this technique is that it is inconsistent, and it is not fully understood why specific dendrites are labeled and others are not. Stronger experimental evidence comes specifically from high-resolution, long-term *in vivo* imaging using the revolutionary two-photon microscopy. This method is much better understood, and its data are more comprehensive. Interestingly, initial results from these experiments show a very stable dendritic structure over long periods of time, while spine growth and destruction (considered in our first case) is *very* active (10). Meanwhile, axonal growth has only been observed as a response to prolonged injury in the brain (1). It follows that our second case seems to be a less common, if useful, means of synaptic plasticity.

***In Vivo* Study of Synapse Dynamics**

In vivo evidence of structural synaptic plasticity is very strong (10). Long-term, high-resolution imaging experiments in the somatosensory cortex have shown that some dendritic spines appear and disappear, and that the rate of turnover is

modulated by sensory experience (11). Figure 3 clearly shows the nature of spine growth and removal.

Figure 3 Temporally examining dendritic spine growth of a mouse barrel cortex *in vivo* over 8 days during somatosensory experiences. **a**, Low-scale magnification of three pyramidal neurons. **b**, Greater magnification of one apical tuft (yellow box in **a**). **c**, High-resolution time-lapse images of a dendritic region (yellow box in **b**). Examples of transient, semi-stable and stable spines are labeled with blue, red and yellow arrowheads, respectively. Scale bar: 100 μm in **a**, 50 μm in **b**, 5 μm in **c**. This figure was adapted from its original version published in (11).

In one study of the adult cortex, chronic time-lapse imaging revealed that spines were dynamic: about 20% of spines were gone from one day to the next, while about 60% of spines persisted for at least 8 days. Supporting our conclusion in §2 that most synapse changes in the adult cortex are driven by short range dynamics (*e.g.* spine growth and

retraction), there was no observed growth or retraction of full dendritic or axonal branching over several weeks (11).

In addition, boutons appear and disappear on all axon types, while bouton densities remain stable. There is a significant natural variation among the alternative bouton types: for example, on thalamocortical axons, the vast majority of boutons persist for 9 months or more, while those *en passant* boutons on pyramidal cell axons have a turnover rate of over 20% in a single month. Further, *terminaux* boutons have a turnover rate of over 50% in a single month (10). This variability shows that cell type is very important in ultimately determining the dynamics of synapse formation. When compared to the turnover rate of dendritic spines, boutons tend to be less dynamic, suggesting that spines (our postsynaptic unit) and boutons (our presynaptic unit) are not strictly correlated or broadly integrated in their growth (12).

Interestingly, *in vivo* evidence has shown a strong correlation between spine growth in the neocortex and the age of the mammal being examined. In the developing neocortex, spines are being generated and reduced at a very rapid rate, while in the adult neocortex spine growth is much more stable (13). What does this indicate? It shows that during the developmental critical period of an animal, when the brain displays a heightened sensitivity to certain environmental stimuli such as sensory experiences, dendritic spine growth is *physically responsible* for the development of neural circuits; the adult neocortex does not learn as easily because spine growth is not as rapid, and hence synapse dynamics are not as active.

What are the lifetimes of spines? Time-lapse studies show a great diversity, but there are some general considerations to be made. The first is most spines that grow *de novo* are likely to perish within a few days, while those spines that survive for a week are likely to persist for several months (14). Larger spines tend to live longer, but this does not always hold true (10). Some studies have attempted to classify spines into relatively discrete

morphologies to discern structural variations among the so-called classifications. The more accurate perception, however, seems to be that spines simply grow along a structural continuum (14). It is more useful to analyze the dimensions of spines quantitatively and correlate this to functionality (a biophysical approach) than to assign superficial labels (*e.g.* mushroom spines).

Perhaps more interestingly, there is an emerging body of evidence that shows a subpopulation of boutons and axons to be relatively stable over the entire lifetime of a mouse. Furthermore, the sizes of individual boutons and spines in this group remain relatively stable. How can this be so, when proteins in synapses are known to have a high turnover rate? One mechanism for measuring *how* the strength and size of a synapse changes over long periods of time is through the labeling of postsynaptic density protein 95 (PSD-95) with photo-activatable GFP (paGFP), which is a building block for the synapse. In this fashion, the motion of PSD-95 in and out of postsynaptic densities can be measured *in vivo* (15). Applications of this method have shown two important points: that PSD-95 indeed has a very short lifetime (less than one hour) and is constantly in flux throughout the synapse, but also that the size of the spine being observed is proportional to the *amount* of PSD-95 being diffused. In other words, the size of spines, and hence synapses, is both carefully and very actively regulated through an equilibrium-based process; neural circuits maintain the size and stability of synapse connections through a constant influx of carefully sized proteins to each and every existing connection. No connection can live without this stream of specialized food. But if the size and stability of these connections are so precisely regulated, what is the physical stimulus that disrupts this chemical equilibrium in one direction (protein build-up) or the other (protein loss)? The answer is *sensory experience*.

Stimulated Synaptic Plasticity

Functional circuits in the adult neocortex are wired by new experiences. Evidence shows that spines

are created and destroyed based upon experience with enriched environments, as well as long-term sensory stimulation and deprivation. In addition, the density of spines, and thus synapses, change as a function of experience (16). Figure 4 shows spine dynamics data from mice that suffered focal lesions through a concentrated laser.

Figure 4 Experience-dependent spine plasticity in the adult neocortex exemplified *in vivo*. **a**, Time-lapse of dendritic spines in the visual cortex after a unilateral focal lesion in the retina. Some spines persist for more than two months (yellow arrowhead), while most spines are actually lost because of the trauma (green arrowhead) but replaced by new persistent spines (orange arrowhead). **b**, Dendritic spines in or near the functionally connected area to the lesion show much higher rates of dissolution than the control. **c**, With increased spine death also comes increased persistence of new spines as replacements. Ultimately, this figure shows that the spine growth is functionally related to sensory experience. This figure was adapted from its original publication in (10).

In this experiment (Figure 4), about 90% of the previously existing spines were replaced within 2

months of a focal retinal lesion, compared to less than 40% in controls. This suggests that functional reorganization is associated with a near-complete exchange of inputs on dendrites of layer 5 pyramidal cells (17). In other words, synapses rewire as a means of recovering from an experience. In the process, synaptic matrices bolster their response to similar future experiences.

This turnover and potentiation of spines as a result of sensory stimulation has been shown in other experiments as well. Parallel to the retinal lesion experiment, trimming the whiskers of a mouse also decreases the survival fraction of existing spines (due to an increased loss of persistent spines), and increases the fraction of new persistent spines, relative to a control (18). Alternatively, modern imaging experiments have tracked dendritic spines in the motor cortex during motor learning. What happens? Training of an exercise sparks the growth of new dendritic spines, and with more training, the network of spines becomes more and more robust (19). The direct connection between learning and spine reorganization is very insightful into the nature of functional memory.

Considered together, these experiments highlight the physical role of synapse structural dynamics in a neural circuit's functional capacity to guide the adaption of physiological responses to new environmental stimuli. Characterizing the nature of this rewiring seems to be the key to decoding the nature of functional memory and learning, two processes that are probably indistinguishable at the biophysical level.

Discussion

Having examined the biophysics of synaptic dynamics, we are now positioned to characterize the system that allows for sensory information encryption and use. First, we consider alternative applications of information systems to help clarify how we might approach this problem (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Conceptual display of information encryption systems to help characterize that of neural circuits. **a**, Computers save digital information through organization of magnetized bits. **b**, Species save hereditary information through sequencing of nucleotides. **c**, How neural circuits save sensory information is not clear, but evidence suggests that functional cognition abilities are wired into the neural circuit through changes in structural synaptic matrices. This is an original figure.

If our quest was to identify the physical substrate for long-term storage of information in a species, we could target DNA, recognize the fundamental and functional nature that the sequence of nucleotides has, and pursue a numerical analysis of how certain sequences (*i.e.* genes) precisely *inform* cells to build specific chains of amino acids, which fold into catalytic proteins. In a similar fashion, modern computers store information by magnetizing ferromagnetic material in a directional dichotomy, theoretically representing either a 0 or a 1, so that this data can then be read back by detecting the magnetization of the material over a staggering array of binary digits. In both of these examples, we are interested in the macroscopic interplay of an enormous number of these units of function. It is in this framework that we might be inclined to ask: what are the binary digits for functional memory?

The answer is that they probably don't exist: neural circuits do not seem to organize

electrochemically-translated sensory input * (*i.e.* ETSI; see Figure 6a) in a discrete or dichotomic fashion. It follows that there may not exist any linear unit of functional memory. However, there absolutely must exist a system. Based upon the biophysical information reviewed in this investigation, it is reasonable for us to believe that neural circuits encrypt and use sensory information through an electrochemical system of *non-linear instructional synapse matrices*.

In describing a neural circuit's processing of ETSI as *instructional*, I am taking into consideration the causal relationships between specific variables of connected neurons, such as membrane action-potential and electrical firing rate, which physically

**Electrochemically-translated sensory input* is defined here as the unique and precise physical organization of electricity and chemicals, derived from a sensory experience, which the neocortex processes. Every sense (sight, touch, *etc.*) is translated into this common language of the brain.

Figure 6 Neural circuit treatment of electrochemically-translated sensory input (ETSI). **a**, An organ translates sensory input into an equivalent (\Leftrightarrow) combination of electricity and chemicals (*i.e.* ETSI). **b**, The exact matrices excited over time is a function, f , of the ETSI. Here, we define the ETSI to be equal to a specific sensory input: \dagger . We examine the unique neuron/axon/dendrite routes that are excited in a neuron culture for two scenarios of this sensory input \dagger : before a critical synapse change (blue), and after (yellow). The red circle shows where the change occurs (see Figure 2 for visual insight). This figure shows how synapse dynamics redefine f (ETSI) non-linearly. The colorless part of (b), a culture of rat hippocampal neurons, is courtesy of Paul De Koninck. This is an original figure.

feed into each other, physically fueled and precisely instructed by the ESTI. Furthermore, I am respecting that this is a complex combinatorial system by describing it as non-linear.

With this understanding, I consider the *matrices* of synaptic connections (Figure 6b). Indeed, we have observed strong evidence for a functional relationship between synapse wiring and sensory experiences, as seen *in vivo* (1, 10, 18, 19), which testifies to the power of custom cortical wiring. It follows that a specific neuron/axon/dendrite matrix excited through ETSI is directly correlated with a specific sensory experience. Thus, collective cognition abilities emerge (3) from *associations* of these excitation matrices.

New ETSI, or old ETSI flowing through new synaptic connections, may not be able to activate a familiar array of associated matrices (*i.e.* a functional memory), because the synaptic connections among these matrices may not yet be

wired yet; *i.e.* all of the micro-systems of thinking have not yet become one macro-system. In this case, the new ETSI (or forgotten ETSI) does not make sense.

The mammalian brain, however, has the ability to *learn*. Learning seems to be: selective production of new synaptic connections, and divestment in the chemical equilibrium sustaining others, which integrates previously disparate instructional matrices. New functional memories can be encrypted by connecting only a few synapses (*e.g.* learning a new word); or perhaps by massive restructuring (*e.g.* understanding the general theory of relativity; see 17).

Once a circuit has been rewired, it can route familiar ETSI through a custom-designed non-linear instructional synapse matrix to trigger a familiar association of electrical action-responses (*i.e.* a familiar *train* of thought can be *remembered*).

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